

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Methodologies for determining the abundance of earthworms

Various methods have been developed for studying soil organisms, and the choice of method depends on the study's objectives, cost, time required, and prior experience with the method. The physical properties of each soil sample, including soil temperature and moisture, affect the effectiveness of the methods.

Hand-sorting method - this is the most commonly used method, simple and does not require special equipment or skills. The excavation is square-shaped, with the area depending on the research task, usually 50 x 50 cm or 25 x 25 cm. The depth of the excavation is 40-50 cm. The excavated soil is placed on plastic sheeting and sorted manually. This method is standardized by ISO standard ISO 23611-1:2018.

Mustard powder solution (MPS) method - it is a natural substance that does not harm plants and other soil organisms, and it is harmless to the soil. Remove plant material from the sample square (50 x 50 cm or 25 x 25 cm) until the soil surface

is visible. Then, cover the sample square with a 5% MPS. Collect the earthworms that appear on the surface. After a few minutes, repeat the treatment of the sample square with the MPS. This allows you to collect even those earthworms that are located in deep burrows.

Combined method - this is a combination of the hand-sorting method and additional treatment of the excavation bottom with an extraction solution. It is recommended to use a MPS as the extraction solution.

The abundance of earthworms is usually presented as individuals per square meter. Various methods are used to obtain the biomass of earthworms. The two most common methods are to weigh the earthworms alive after washing or to weigh the earthworms alive after washing and after cleaning the gut contents on moist filter paper at a temperature of 4-6°C for 48 hours.

1. Application of mustard powder aqueous solution. Photo Kuu, A.

2. Soil cube for the handsorting of earthworms. Photo Shanskiy, M.

KEYWORDS

Hand-sorting, mustard powder solution, methods, earthworms

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

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